

Tuning Technology for Adaptable Radar Bandwidth

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Abstract—The spectrum sensing, multi-optimization (SS-MO) technique is investigated to provide a radar with frequency agility and high signal to interference plus noise ratio (SINR). The SS-MO technique requires tuning technology to reconfigure the operating bandwidth of the radar. Fast tuning speeds are needed in order to maintain the coherent processing interval (CPI) length; otherwise, the time available for the radar emission is decreased and results in radiating fewer pulses on target thereby reducing SINR. In this paper several tuning technology categories are investigated for the SS-MO technique. It will be shown how faster tuning technology provides the SS-MO technique with the capability to maintain high levels of SINR in the presence of high power radio frequency interference (RFI).

Keywords—radar, tuning technology, spectrum sharing, spectrum sensing, optimization, waveform agility

I. INTRODUCTION

Radio frequency (RF) interference (RFI) is a growing challenge for radar. RFI is caused by RF sources operating in band and out of band to the radar [1], which has been shown to degrade radar performance [2]. This problem is exacerbated by the potential new FCC regulations specified by the National Broadcast Plan, which would require government radar systems to share spectrum with commercial communication systems [3]. Clearly radars need a way to coexist in the electromagnetic environment (EME) by 1) detecting and mitigating interference from RF sources; 2) identifying and/or cooperating with RF systems in order to avoid causing interference; 3) modifying the radars' bandwidth to comply with regulations.

A potential solution that addresses these challenges is the spectrum sensing, multi-objective optimization (SS-MO) technique [4]. This technique passively monitors the operating band of the radar for RFI during radar operation. The technique identifies a continuous frequency sub-band that maximizes both signal to interference plus noise ratio (SINR) and bandwidth. Reconfigurable filters then tune to this optimal sub-band. The tunable filters mitigate unwanted RFI and must support a limitless number of synthesized waveforms that vary in frequency, power, phase, modulation, and duty cycle.

The SS-MO technique is implemented at the start of the coherent processing interval (CPI) so that the radar has an up-to-date measure of the RFI. In this development, the RFI is assumed to be stationary over the CPI. Ideally the radar would then transmit N pulses for the remainder of the CPI; however, since the radar devotes resources to the implementation of the SS-MO technique, additional time is needed. For a radar system design requiring fixed timelines (i.e. a constant CPI), this added processing time is compensated by reducing the number of pulses on target, which consequently decreases the

SINR. Clearly the computational complexity of the SS-MO technique should be at a minimum. The time needed to reconfigure the filters must also be at a minimum. Assuming that everything else is minimized, the problem then becomes that of choosing tunable filter technology that supports a rapid tuning speed while maintaining a high quality performance.

In this paper, tuning speed categories (slow, medium, fast) are investigated for the SS-MO technique. The analysis is broadly applicable to multiple tuning technology types to include RF microelectromechanical systems (MEMS), barium-strontium-titanate (BST), Schottky Diode, and yttrium-iron-garnet (YIG). The tuning technology must provide high-performance solutions for tunable filters that have the capability to: configure the transmitter and receiver to support waveform adaptation (for both narrowband and wideband applications); reject high-powered interference and not introduce additional intermodulation products.

The goal of this investigation is to quantify the SINR produced by the SS-MO technique for various RFI measurements. The SINR is dependent on: 1) the number of pulses on target, a direct result of the tuning speed; 2) an empirical estimate of the interference and noise in the sub-band chosen by the SS-MO technique.

II. SPECTRUM SENSING FOR RADAR

An overview of the SS-MO technique is discussed in this section. Full details of this technique are discussed in [4, 5] where it is shown that the SINR and peak-to-average-sidelobe ratio are significantly improved. A block diagram of the SS-MO technique for radar is illustrated in Fig. 1. Spectrum sensing is used to passively monitor a fixed frequency band, B , of interest (i.e., the overall bandwidth). The spectrum sensing receiver receives, digitizes, and processes the observed RF spectrum to generate a power spectrum of size M using the fast Fourier transform.

Fig. 1. Spectrum sensing, multi-objective optimization radar technique.

The power spectrum is used to form two objective functions. The first objective function, SINR, is defined as

$$Z_1(\beta, f) = P_r(\beta) / \Gamma(\beta, f), \quad (1)$$

where $\Gamma(\beta, f)$ is an empirical estimate of the interference and noise for various center frequency, f , and sub-band, $\beta \in B$, combinations; this empirical estimate is formed using the power spectrum. $P_r(\beta)$ is the receive power modeled using the radar range equation. The first goal of the multi-objective optimization technique is to adjust β and f in order to maximize (1). The receive power is defined as

$$P_r(\beta) = P_t G^2 \lambda^2 \sigma N \tau \beta / [(4\pi)^3 R^4] = CN\tau\beta, \quad (2)$$

where P_t is the peak transmit power of the radar, G is the antenna gain, λ is the wavelength of the carrier frequency, R is the range to target, τ is the radar pulse width, N is the number of pulses transmitted by the radar within the CPI, and C is a constant that replaces the product of the constant radar parameters. Eq. (2) supports a linear frequency modulated, pulse compression waveform with the time-bandwidth product $\tau\beta$. Note that the SS-MO technique can support multiple waveforms and could be quite complementary to digitally-tunable waveforms such as those described in [6]. The sub-band is the second objective function and defined as

$$Z_2(\beta) = \beta. \quad (3)$$

The second goal of the multi-objective optimization technique is to adjust β in order to maximize (3); this occurs when $\beta = B$.

Next define the decision variable $x = \{\beta, f\}$ that forms the solution space X . The overall goal of the optimization process is to adjust the decision variable $x = \{\beta, f\}$ to find $x^* = \{\beta^*, f^*\}$ such that the objection functions in (1) and (3) are maximized:

$$Z(\beta^*, f^*) = \{Z_1(\beta^*, f^*), Z_2(\beta^*)\} \quad (4)$$

subject to $Z_1(\beta^*, f^*) \geq Z_{1,min}$ and $Z_2(\beta^*) \geq Z_{2,min}$, where $Z_{1,min}$ and $Z_{2,min}$ are the minimum SINR and bandwidth (respectively) allowable for radar operation. Note that the minimum bandwidth must satisfy the time-bandwidth requirement of $\tau\beta \geq 100$ so that 98-99% of the waveform energy is contained within β . Since the tuning technology tunes to β , the minimum bandwidth must also satisfy a fast steady-state filter response in order to avoid transients.

After (4) is estimated, the RF front-end filter is tuned. The radar system then synthesizes the appropriate waveform and transmits this waveform into the EME for the remainder of the CPI. The CPI for radar operation is defined as

$$T = T_S + T_O + T_F + T_R \quad (5)$$

where T_S is the spectrum sensing collection time, T_O is the multi-objective optimization processing time, T_F is the filter tuning time (i.e. the time needed to tune the filter to β), and T_R is the radar operation time. Assuming a non-fading channel, the CPI timing diagram for the SS-MO technique is shown in Fig. 2. In this development the computational complexity needed to solve (4) is small such that $T_S + T_O \ll T_F$; the filter tuning time is therefore the bottleneck that potentially delays radar spectrum sensing.

Fig. 2: CPI timing diagram for the SS-MO technique.

This paper considers radars that employ a CPI in the microseconds. A range of radar sensor technology use this CPI, including ultra-wideband synthetic aperture radar (SAR), airborne tracking radar, and ground penetrating radar (GPR) of 136 – 680 μ s as provided in [7]. The radar will require different tuning technology capabilities depending on the application. Radar applications, like the detection of electronic components [8], require that the tuning technology have low insertion loss and high linearity while providing the desired filter response.

We consider three general groups of tuning technology based on their speeds [9]. The first category, C1, constitutes tuning times between 1 to 300 μ s; the second category, C2, has tuning times between 300 and 600 μ s; and the final category, C3, constitutes tuning times between 600 and 900 μ s.

III. EXPERIMENT AND ANALYSIS

The SS-MO technique is used to process four individual RF spectra consisting of different interference and noise power levels. The spectral data were collected by an Agilent Technologies N9342CN handheld spectrum analyzer using an AOR DA3200 discone antenna. The spectrum analyzer monitored a bandwidth $B = 100$ MHz using 100 kHz frequency resolution at the following center frequencies (F_c): 286 MHz, 437 MHz, 778 MHz, and 813 MHz. Each spectrum corresponds to $M = 1000$ frequency bins per spectrum. The thermal noise of the spectrum analyzer is $P_N = -91$ dBm.

Eq. (4) is solved using a linear weighting function [4]. The boundary conditions used for the SS-MO technique are $Z_{1,min} = 0.1$ and $Z_{2,min} = 10$ MHz. The radar range equation parameters are defined as $\tau = 10$ μ s and $C = 4.1 \times 10^{-16}$. C is calculated using (2) assuming that the SINR upper limit is set to 30; the SINR upper limit is achieved when no RFI is present ($\Gamma(\beta, f)$ defaults to the thermal noise of -91 dBm) and the full bandwidth is utilized ($\beta = B$). The radar CPI is defined as 900 μ s corresponding to $N = 45$ radar pulses, where the pulse repetition interval (PRI) is 20 μ s.

The spectra are illustrated in Fig. 3 ordered from smallest to largest RFI power level. The RFI power level is measured using the average power estimate $P_a = \sum \theta_i / M$. The sub-band selected by the SS-MO technique is illustrated by the green horizontal line. The spectrum in Fig. 3a corresponds to thermal noise with $F_c = 286$ MHz and $P_a = -91$ dBm. The SS-MO technique selects the full bandwidth $\beta = B$, the appropriate choice given that no interference is present in the RF spectrum. The spectrum in Fig. 3b corresponds to $F_c = 813$ MHz with an increased $P_a = -85$ dBm. The SS-MO technique selects $\beta = 76.4$ MHz with $P_a = -91$ dBm (equal to thermal noise). The spectrum in Fig. 3c

corresponds to $F_c = 778$ MHz with $P_a = -76$ dBm. The SS-MO technique selects $\beta = 53.3$ MHz with $P_a = -91$ dBm; once again the thermal noise is selected. The spectrum in Fig. 3d corresponds to $F_c = 437$ MHz with $P_a = -55$ dBm. Narrowband, high-power interference is present in this spectrum. The SS-MO technique selects $\beta = 73.7$ MHz with energy equal to -89.9 dBm. As shown, the SS-MO technique significantly reduces the average RFI power in the RF spectrum as compared to the full bandwidth.

Fig. 3: Measured power spectrums at different RFI power levels. The sub-band estimated by the SS-MO technique is illustrated in green.

The SINR for the spectra of Fig. 3 are shown in Fig. 4. The graphs display the SINR for each tuning time category, and the SINR using the full bandwidth (assuming no SS-MO). As the tuning time of the filter T_F increases, the number of pulses decrease thus decreasing the SINR. The graphs also display a crossover point to indicate the maximum T_F allowable by the tuning technology for SS-MO to have an advantage over full bandwidth; the green shaded area indicates the tuning technology categories where using SS-MO is advantageous over full bandwidth.

Fig. 4a shows the SINR for the spectrum of Fig. 3a, where the full bandwidth (red line) maintains a higher SINR as T_F increases. Hence, since no interference is present, the SS-MO technique is not needed. Fig. 4b shows the SINR for the spectrum of Fig. 3b. The SS-MO technique maintains higher SINR for tuning times of $580 \mu\text{s}$ or less, which includes the C1 category and the majority of the C2 category. For this RFI the SS-MO technique shows an advantage over using the full bandwidth. Fig. 4c shows the SINR for the spectrum of Fig. 3c. The SS-MO technique maintains higher SINR for tuning times of $860 \mu\text{s}$ or less; this includes almost all the categories. Once again the SS-MO technique shows an advantage over using the full bandwidth. Fig. 4d shows the SINR for the spectrum of Fig. 3d. The SS-MO technique maintains higher SINR for all categories and has a clear advantage of maintaining SINR in the presence of high power interference.

Fig. 4: SINR results for the SS-MO technique and the full bandwidth.

IV. CONCLUSION

The SINR of the SS-MO technique depends on an empirical estimate of the RFI and the number of pulses on target. As the tuning time of the filter technology increases the number of pulses on target decreases, which consequently decreases the SINR. The results indicate that RFI significantly degrades SINR and that the additional time needed for tuning is advantageous. The only exception to this conclusion is when minimal RFI is present in the operating band of the radar (*i.e.*, the noise-only scenario in Fig. 2a); all other results indicate the advantage of the SS-MO technique utilizing tunable components.

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